

STATISTICAL LIFE PREDICTION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CF/PP TAPE UNDER CREEP TENSION LOAD

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Introduction

A carbon fiber / polypropylene unidirectional sheet (CF/PP UD sheet) has been developed by Mitsui Chemicals Inc. from a new polyolefin base sizing agent for carbon fiber as well as the effective PP modification brings good compatibility with PP to improve the fiber matrix adhesion.

The statistical life prediction of CF/PP UD sheet is performed.

1. A tensile test method for creep strength and static strength at elevated temperatures was developed for CF/PP UD tape. And static strengths of CF/PP UD tape are experimentally and statistically measured at various temperatures.
2. The creep failure times of CF/PP UD tape at a constant load and a temperature are measured experimentally and probabilistically for comparison with the predicted ones.
3. The statistical long-term life prediction of CF/PP UD tape under tension load is performed.

SEM image of CF/PP after specimen fracture.

Formulation for Statistical Creep Life Time

The statistical time and temperature dependent static strength σ_s is given by Eq.(1) based on two conditions: (A) failure probability is independent of the temperature and load histories and (B) time-dependent and temperature-dependent strength is controlled by the matrix resin viscoelasticity. Here P_f is failure probability, t and t_0 are failure time and reference failure time, T is temperature, T_0 is reference temperature, σ_0 and α are scale and shape parameters on the Weibull distribution of static strength. n_R is viscoelastic parameter. E_r is relaxation moduli and E_s^* is viscoelastic moduli of matrix resin for the static load with a constant strain rate. α_c is shape parameter of tensile strength of a single carbon fiber.

$$\log \sigma_s = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_s^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$E_s^*(t, T) = E_r(t/2, T) \quad (2)$$

$$n_R = 1/2\alpha_c \quad (3)$$

The statistical creep strength σ_c is expressed by Eq.(4). Here E_c^* is viscoelastic modulus for a constant stress load. The shifting amount $\log A$ based on Christensen's theory for viscoelastic crack kinetics is a function of K_R . m_R is the slope of logarithmic creep compliance of matrix resin against logarithmic time.

$$\log \sigma_c = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_c^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$E_c^*(t, T) = E_s^*(At, T) = E_r(At/2, T) \quad (5)$$

$$\log A = \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{k_R} \right), \quad k_R = n_R m_R \quad (6)$$

Life Time Prediction and Experimental Verification

Creep testing machines with constant temperature chambers

Failure probability against creep failure time for CF/PP UD tape at 120°C

Failure probability against creep failure time for CF/PP UD tape

The Static Tension Test and Model Parameters

The scale parameter σ_0 decreases according to the temperature raise, the shape parameter α maintains almost a constant value except those at 150°C. This data obeys Christensen's theory for viscoelastic crack kinetics.

Weibull distributions of static tensile strength of CF/PP UD tape

Creep compliance of PP

Statistical static strength of CF/PP UD tape against viscoelastic compliance of PP

Conclusion and Acknowledgments

This study examines prediction of the statistical life time for this developed CF/PP UD sheet under creep tension loading. The validity of formulation for the statistical time and temperature dependent static and creep strengths was clarified experimentally for tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CF/PP UD tape using our developed CF/PP UD tape testing system. Results clarified that the long-term creep failure time of CF/PP UD tape under tension loading can be readily inferred statistically using the results of static tests at various temperatures.

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